

Improving the technology of energy-saving products from local raw materials

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Abstract: Continuous population growth leads to an increase in overall energy consumption, which, in turn, can lead to serious consequences of climate change. Two-thirds of the world's greenhouse gases come from the production and use of energy resources. Global warming is not only an increase in average temperature, but also causes an imbalance of weather throughout the planet, which, in turn, causes various natural disasters. This article describes the improvement of technology for producing energy-saving products from local raw materials.

Key words: Raw materials, local, economical, energy, innovative, technology.

To avoid these risks, many countries are actively moving towards a clean, smart and secure energy system by developing and implementing energy-saving technologies in the design and construction of energy-efficient and low-carbon buildings. Countries are transitioning to energy efficient (EE) and low carbon (LC) construction in different ways. From 2019, all new buildings built in the European Union (EU) are expected to meet passive housing standards, and from 2021, these standards will apply to other buildings. There are several thousand energy-efficient homes in Europe, and this number continues to grow. The basic concept of a passive house is to reduce heat loss through the walls, roof and windows of buildings, high-quality thermal insulation of the external surfaces of the building walls, triple glazing, sealing the building structure and improving thermal insulation. heat

recovery and ventilation system. “Passive” home heating uses solar energy, internal heat sources and warm air produced by air recovery in the ventilation system.

It is possible to increase the energy efficiency of buildings built in the last century without using energy-saving technologies. For example, a construction company in Berlin, Germany, carried out a major renovation of an eight-story building built in the 1950s. In these buildings, the renovation project includes updating the ventilation systems, insulating the facade walls, and installing a solar panel system on the roof and facade of the building. The energy generated by solar panels is stored in battery cells and used to supply electricity to households, as well as hot water and heating systems. Thanks to new construction technologies and materials, heat consumption in apartments is reduced by 85%, 100% autonomous heating and 50% of the required electricity are provided.

Renovated energy-efficient apartment building in Berlin The Dutch government is improving the energy efficiency of existing buildings as part of the Energiesprong program the country launched in 2010. This program retrofits existing buildings to high energy efficiency standards, turning them into net-zero energy buildings. Zero energy is the ability of a building to independently produce all the energy needed to power its occupants. Pilot projects for the modernization of buildings under this program have already started in the UK, Canada, the USA and France.

Modernized houses in the village of Sneathon, located on the outskirts of Nottingham, England.

According to the European Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), all buildings constructed in the European Union must meet low or zero energy building standards. In addition, energy performance certificates in the European Union are mandatory for buildings, and these certificates must be presented to tenants and buyers. A number of studies in Europe, including Ireland, the

Netherlands, Germany and Sweden, show that energy-efficient homes command significantly higher rental or sales prices than conventional homes.

Solar settlement Schlierberg in Freiburg, Germany.

Uzbekistan became the first member state of the Global Green Development Institute (GGGI) among the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS). By becoming a member of the institute, Uzbekistan seeks to implement joint projects aimed at stimulating sustainable economic growth and mitigating the risks of climate change through the development of a “green economy” in the face of climate change.

In addition, since 2017, Uzbekistan has been actively moving towards the transition to “green” construction. Providing environmentally friendly living conditions in rural areas, including in cooperation with UNDP and the Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan and on the basis of grants from the Global Environment Facility (GEF) “Support for the development of construction of energy-efficient rural houses in Uzbekistan” is being implemented within the framework of the project. The first component of the project will help Uzbek banks use green mortgages to massively increase demand for ET and KU housing.

As part of the third component of this project, in 2022 it is planned to develop a new regulatory document for the construction of the Passive House and guidelines for it. It is worth noting that one of the first passive houses in Uzbekistan was built in 2011 on the shore of the Charvok reservoir near the village of Burchmulla according to the design of Mansur Zohidov, an associate professor at the Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Civil Engineering.

Despite the fact that measures to introduce green strategies into the economy and construction are being actively taken by the state, it is necessary to increase public awareness and increase public participation in the development and use of energy efficient solutions. Anyone planning to renovate their home can take steps to improve the home's thermal upgrades and energy efficiency. These measures

include high-quality insulation of the walls, roof and floor of the house, replacement of windows and doors. Owners of private houses can also install an innovative heating system with the ability to regulate the room temperature.

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